

FAIR Principles for Training Resources

Group 4 - Reusable

Version 1.0

Introduction

A lot of time and effort goes into developing good training resources so they should be reused.

What does it mean for the training content to be reusable? The FAIR Data and Software Principles focus on optimising use and reuse, including licensing, provenance and domain-relevant community standards [2,3]. The related rules in “Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR” [1] are:

- **Make your training materials (re)usable for trainers**
- **Make your training materials usable for trainees**
- **Make your training materials contribution friendly**

How do you interpret the above rules? What do they mean in practice? Are there any other considerations that should be applied to ensure content is reusable?

In this session we would like you to think about and discuss what it means for the training content to be accessible, and following the instructions included below, formulate a list of specific recommendations for making HPC/RCD/RSE training content more **Reusable**.

Fig 1. Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. The first rule—to share—is the central starting point; the Findability rules include description, identity, and registration; the latter two, together with access rules, correspond to Accessibility; Interoperability stands on its own, with one rule about formats; the remaining four rules cover different aspects of Reusability. Illustration from Luc Wiegiers and Celia van Gelder: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3593257>.

Instructions

The session is split into 3 parts:

- Group discussion (25min)
- Report out recommendations (10min)
- Contribute recommendations to the Best Practices Guide (15min)

Part 1 - Group Discussion:

Please think about and discuss these points:

Notetaker: keep notes in the template below.

- Define your term - **Reusable** - what does it mean in the context of training content?
- How can we evaluate 'reusability' of the existing content?
- How can we make content that is **Reusable**? List as many approaches/implementation options as you can think of given, for example:
 - Size of the training repository
 - Types of material
 - Delivery method
 - Audiences

Part 2 - Report out recommendations

Notetaker: keep notes in the template below.

Synthesize your discussion into best practices recommendations for report out:

- Focus on the 3 points that were most important to your group (that you found most compelling, interesting, controversial)

Part 3 - Contribute recommendations to the Best Practices Guide

Starting with your top three recommendations, please edit and expand on your recommendations and add them to [here](#). If you run out of time during this session, or you are interested in building the [Best Practices Guide](#) you can continue to add content until **1 August 2025**.

Please try to include recommendations for both new and existing training content, keeping in mind the below:

- Different types of content
- Who is the content being FAIRified for?
- What resources or capabilities are needed?
- Are there institutional or regulatory considerations?

Participants

Please assign the following roles in your group to make the most of the available time, including **name, affiliation and email addresses** (for anyone wishing to be involved in the further efforts).

Facilitator:

Note taker:

Reporter:

Team:

Group Discussion Notes

Please try to capture your discussion here:

Add your notes here

Group Recommendations

Please write down your recommendations for making the training resources more **Reusable**:

Add your recommendations here

Content to be added to the Best Practices Guide

The below content will be refined and added to the content FAIRfying Best Practice Guide. Please try to include recommendations for the following three categories:

Evaluating Reusability

How to create reusable resources

How to improve reusability of existing content

Add your content here

References:

- [1] Garcia L, Batut B, Burke ML, Kuzak M, Psomopoulos F, Arcila R, et al. (2020) Ten simple rules for making training materials FAIR. PLoS Comput Biol 16(5): e1007854. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1007854>
- [2] <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- [3] Barker, M., Chue Hong, N.P., Katz, D.S. *et al.* Introducing the FAIR Principles for research software. *Sci Data* 9, 622 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01710-x>